

AN IMPROVED V-LAMBDA SOLUTION
OF THE
MATRIX RICCATI EQUATION⁺

by

Itzhack Y. Bar-Itzhack* and F. Landis Markley**

Flight Dynamics Analysis Branch
NASA - Goddard Space Flight Center
Greenbelt, MD 20771

I. INTRODUCTION

A recent paper [1] introduced a new algorithm for solving the matrix Riccati equation

$$\dot{P}(t) = F(t)P(t) + P(t)F(t)^T + Q(t) - P(t)C(t)P(t)$$

$$P(t_0) = P_0, \quad t > t_0$$

in which Q, C, and P₀ are nxn real symmetric matrices and F is an nxn matrix. The algorithm makes use of the following spectral decomposition of P

$$P(t) = V(t)^T \Lambda(t) V(t)$$

in which Λ is a diagonal matrix of the eigenvalues and V is an orthogonal matrix of the eigenvectors of P. (In the ensuing we will refer to an orthonormal matrix as an orthogonal one). The algorithm, called V-Lambda, possesses all the advantages of a square root algorithm. It requires the solution of two matrix differential equations of the form

$$\dot{\Lambda}(t) = G(t)$$

$$\dot{V}(t) = W(t)V(t) \quad (1)$$

where, obviously, G(t) is diagonal. The matrix W(t) is a skew-symmetric matrix. V is an nxn matrix. The number of scalar integrations implied by (1) is n²; however, the orthogonality of V invokes n(n+1)/2 relations among its elements. Therefore there are really only m=n(n-1)/2 independent elements in V. The burden involved in solving (1) can be reduced by properly defining the m independent parameters of V, solving a differential equation only for them and then performing algebraic computation to transform these m elements into V.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Given the matrix differential equation (1) in which W is a skew symmetric matrix and for which the initial matrix V(t₀) is known to be orthogonal, find the following:

- a) m=n(n-1)/2 parameters which unambiguously define V,

⁺ This paper is a summary of Ref. 2

** NRC-NASA Research Associate. On leave from Technion-Israel Institute of Technology.

* Aerospace Engineer.

- b) the differential equation needed to be solved in order to compute these parameters,
- c) the functional relations between the parameters and V which will enable the computation of V based on the parameters, and
- d) a simple algorithm to implement the solution of the differential equation as well as the computation of V.

III. BACKGROUND MATERIAL

We observe that (1) is identical to the famous differential equation of the 3-D attitude matrix. Two questions that come immediately to mind are: does (1) always yield a solution which is orthogonal? and conversely, do all orthogonal matrices solve such a differential equation? It can be shown [2] that given equation (1) for t₀ < t < t₁ where W^T(t) = -W(t) then V^T(t)V(t) is a constant matrix and if, in addition, the initial matrix V(t₀) is orthogonal, then V(t) is orthogonal too. It is also shown [2] that all orthogonal matrices solve a differential equation having the form of (1).

In view of the preceding, it is realized that the problem we are concerned with is an extension of the three dimensional attitude determination problem and conversely, the latter is a special case of the problem at hand. It is interesting to investigate the various algorithms for 3-D attitude determination and decide which one (if any) of them can be extended to solve the present problem. Such an investigation was carried out in Ref. [2]. The 3-D parametrizations which were investigated are: Euler Angles, the Quaternion and Rodrigues Parameters (also known as Cayley-Rodrigues Parameters or Gibbs vector). It was found that only the Rodrigues Parameters are extendible to a compact easily implementable algorithm. This will be shown in the next section.

IV. EXTENDED RODRIGUES PARAMETERS

The use of the extended Rodrigues parameters hinges on the following theorem on the Cayley Transform:

Theorem IV.1: Let V be an n-th order orthogonal matrix with none of its eigenvalues equal to -1 then

- I) there exists a matrix G defined as follows
- $$G = (I-V)(I+V)^{-1} \quad (2)$$

II) G is skew-symmetric

III) V is the following function of G

$$V = (I-G)(I+G)^{-1} \quad (3)$$

IV) the rate of change of G is given by

$$\dot{G} = -\frac{1}{2}(I+G)W(I+G)^T \quad (4)$$

Proof: For proof see reference [2].

Note [see ref.2] that the condition for the invertibility of (I+G) is that V has no eigenvalues at -1. The parametrization of V by G fails when the latter is the case. However this can be overcome as will be shown in Section V. The parametrization of V by the Extended Rodrigues Parameters is n-dimensional since the proof of the theorem was not restricted to any value of n. What is needed to fully answer our problem is a simple algorithm to implement the solution; this will be presented next.

V. NUMERICAL IMPLEMENTATION

We wish to solve the differential equation (1) using the extended Rodrigues Parameters. The solution process requires first the solution of the differential equation (4) for G and then the computation of V according to (3). There are two caveats which we have to be alerted to. One is the non-existence of G when V has an eigenvalue at -1, and the other is the need to invert the matrix (I+G), which may be so burdensome as to render the whole approach inefficient in comparison with the direct solution of (1). The first problem can be easily avoided if we can keep the elements of G small, for then, as can be readily seen from (3), V is close to I whose eigenvalues are all equal to +1. That is, if we are free to control its size, we can always choose G so small as to make the eigenvalues of V as close to +1 (and thus as far from -1) as we wish. Indeed, we are able to control the magnitude of G. We accomplish it by recomputing V after each integration step of (4) and then setting G=0 for the beginning of the next integration step. That is, at the end of step i+1 we use G_{i+1} to compute $V(t_{i+1}, t_i)$ by

$$V(t_{i+1}, t_i) = (I - G_{i+1})(I + G_{i+1})^{-1} \quad (5)$$

and then we compute $V(t_{i+1})$ using

$$V(t_{i+1}) = V(t_{i+1}, t_i)V(t_i) \quad (6)$$

Finally, we set G to zero and continue to integrate (4) in the next time interval. The ability to use this approach hinges on (6) which is the consequence of a well known property of the solution of first order linear differential equations [2]. While the foregoing policy rids us of the singularity problem it also enables us to easily overcome the need to invert a matrix since for small enough G we can use the following

$$(I+G)^{-1} \approx I-G+G^2-G^3+ \dots$$

The foregoing yields the algorithm presented in Table I.

Table I

Given: $V(t_0) = V_0$ and $W(t)$	
(1)	Initialize $i = 0$
(2)	Set the initial condition $G(t_i)=0$.
(3)	Solve (4) from t_i to t_{i+1} .
(4)	Compute
	$V(t_{i+1}, t_i) =$
	$= I - 2G_{i+1}(I - G_{i+1}[I - G_{i+1}(I - G_{i+1})])$
	$V(t_{i+1}) = V(t_{i+1}, t_i)V(t_i)$
(5)	If t is less than t_f return to step (2) and increase all indices by 1, otherwise STOP.

We ran a 4th dimensional example [see 2]. Equation (1) was solved for reference which was denoted by V_r . The algorithm generated V. An error matrix $E = V - V_r$ and its Euclidean norm, e , were computed. We ran examples in which we let V_r change considerably. A typical error figure was $e = 0.56724776E-07$.

Note that the algorithm presented in Table I uses a series truncated after the 4th power of G (step no. 4). This is based on the results shown in Table II in [2]. In that table it is shown that there is a distinct power beyond which the addition of more terms yields little return.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents an improved algorithm for computing the V-Lambda solution of the matrix Riccati equation. The improvement is expressed in the reduction of the computational load which is based on the orthogonality of the eigenvector matrix that has to be solved for. The orthogonality constraint reduces the number of independent parameters which define the matrix from n^2 to $n(n-1)/2$. The paper shows how to specify them, how to solve for them and how to form from them the needed eigenvector matrix.

In the search for suitable parameters, the analogy between our problem and the problem of attitude determination is exploited which results in our choice of Rodrigues parameters. The paper extends the 3-D parameters to n-D and supplies the necessary algorithm for computing the eigenvector matrix using the extended Rodrigues parameters. A 4-D example is presented which demonstrates the accuracy of the algorithm.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Oshman and I. Y. Bar-Itzhack, "Eigenfactor Solution of the Matrix Riccati Equation - a Continuous Square Root Algorithm," IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control, Vol. AC-30, No. 10, October 1985, pp. 971-978.
- [2] I. Y. Bar-Itzhack and F. Landis Markley, "Minimal Parameter Solution of the Orthogonal Matrix Differential Equation," NASA TM-4043, June 1988.